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**MASTER'S PHOTO ART PROJECT
"NEVER AGAIN?!"****Eduard Stranadko^{1a}, Anastasiia Kanailo^{2a}**

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**МАГІСТЕРСЬКИЙ ФОТОМИСТЕЦЬКИЙ ПРОЄКТ
«НІКОЛИ ЗНОВУ?!»****Едуард Странадко^{1a}, Анастасія Канайло^{2a}**

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The author's idea for the Master's photo art project was to create a photo project about the elderly who are over 80 years old. It was based on the desire to reveal the inner world and life experience of the elderly. The photo project reflects not only the external beauty of the aged but also the deep emotions captured in the eyes and expressions of the characters.

The series consists of portraits of both men and women that become a kind of story, telling the story of the courage, resilience and inner strength of those who witnessed the remarkable historical events over many decades. These photographs, which convey expressive emotions of pain and fatigue, try not only to capture the physical appearance of the heroes but also to convey their experience, courage and unwavering belief in peace and justice, even in the most challenging times for Ukraine.

Through the details on the faces, one can feel the deep emotional grief and the burden of life experiences placed on these people's shoulders over the years. The eyes are the centrepiece of the photographs and attract special attention. They are imbued with pain and sadness from having to relive the war period. The deep wrinkles around the eyes add to the intense expressiveness, showing that time has taken its toll and left its marks on the faces. The sad eyes and closed lips express fatigue and exhaustion, indicating the burden of the years behind the characters. Some of them still have hope for liberation from physical or emotional suffering, while others are depressed and hopeless.

This photo project was filmed to preserve and share the extraordinary experiences of older people who have lived through remarkable events in the history of the world and Ukraine. They have witnessed global war, regime change, and democratic transformation and are now facing aggression that is causing heavy damage and suffering to their homeland. For decades, these people have lived with the belief that war would never come to their homes again, but they have become hostages to the sick ambitions of a Kremlin politician.

Each photographic image in this project aims to penetrate the heart and soul of the viewer. It creates an invisible connection with the subject, allowing you to feel the wisdom, strength and at the same time vulnerability of the characters.

Keywords: photography; war; portrait photography; documentation; conflict; emotions; historical memory

The project's photographer is Anastasiia Kanailo,
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Photo No. 1

129

**"Moments of Tired Experience"
from the Master's photo art project
"Never Again?!"**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 135 mm f/2.0 L USM

Settings:

135 mm | F/2 | ISO 160 | 1/250 s

Image No. 1 edited with Adobe Photoshop 2022:

- Edit exposure, shadow, contrast, and saturation
- Converting the photo to black and white

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 2

**"Witnesses of Age:
Portraits of Wisdom
and Endurance" from the
Master's photo art project
"Never Again?!"**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 135 mm f/2.0 L USM

Settings:

135 mm | F/4 | ISO 1250 | 1/1000 s

**Image No. 2 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Edit exposure, shadow, contrast, and saturation
- Framing
- Convert the photo to black and white

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 3

131

**"Reflections of Resilience" from the Master's
photo art project "Never Again?!"**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 135 mm f/2.0 L USM

Settings:

135 mm | F/2 | ISO 320 | 1/160s

**Image No. 3 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Edit exposure, shadow, contrast, and saturation
- Convert the photo to black and white

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 4

"Tired Eyes"
from the Master's
photo art project
"Never Again?!"

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 135 mm f/2.0 L USM

Settings:

135 mm | F/2 | ISO 160 | 1/800 s

**Image No. 4 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Editing exposure, shadow, contrast and saturation
- Framing
- Converting the image to black and white

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 5

**"Longing of Age:
Reflection of the Weight
of Life" from the master's
photo art project
"Never Again?!"**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 135 mm f/2.0 L USM

Settings:

135 mm | F/2 | ISO 160 | 1/800 s

**Image No. 5 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Editing exposure, shadow, contrast and saturation
- Framing
- Converting the image to black and white

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 6

134

**"A Portrait that
Impresses with Wisdom"
from the Master's
photo art project
"Never Again?!"**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 135 mm f/2.0 L USM

Settings:

135 mm | F/2 | ISO 200 | 1/800 s

**Image No. 6 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Edit exposure, shadow, contrast, and saturation
- Convert the photo to black and white

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 7

135

**"A Glance that Flows
with Time" from the
Master's photo art project
"Never Again?!"**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 135 mm f/2.0 L USM

Settings:

135 mm | F/2 | ISO 320 | 1/250 s

**Image No. 7 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Editing exposure, shadow, contrast and saturation
- Framing
- Converting the image to black and white

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 8

**"Portraiture of Calm"
from the Master's
photo art project
"Never Again?!"**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 135 mm f/2.0 L USM

Settings:

135 mm | F/2 | ISO 320 | 1/250 s

**Image No. 8 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Editing exposure, shadow, contrast and saturation
- Framing
- Converting the image to black and white

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 9

137

**"Imprints of War and Faith"
from the Master's
photo project
"Never Again?"**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 135 mm f/2.0 L USM

Settings:

135 mm | F/2 | ISO 250 | 1/800 s

**Image No. 9 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Editing exposure, shadow, contrast and saturation
- Framing
- Converting the image to black and white

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 10

**"Memories"
from the Master's
photo art project
"Never Again?"**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 135 mm f/2.0 L USM

Settings:

135 mm | F/2 | ISO 640 | 1/1000 s

**Image No. 10 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Editing exposure, shadow, contrast and saturation
- Framing
- Converting the image to black and white

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 11

**“Clenched Lips”
from the Master’s
photo art project
“Never Again?!”**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 135 mm f/2.0 L USM

Settings:

135 mm | F/2 | ISO 1200 | 1/200 s

**Image No. 11 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Editing exposure, shadow, contrast and saturation
- Framing
- Convert photos to black and white

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 12

140

**"The Burden of the Years"
from the Master's
photo art project
"Never Again?!"**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 135 mm f/2.0 L USM

Settings:

135 mm | F/2 | ISO 1200 | 1/200 s

**Image No. 12 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Editing exposure, shadow, contrast and saturation
- Framing
- Convert photos to black and white

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 13

**“Worn-out Hands: Symbols of Time Passing”
from the Master’s photo art project “Never Again?!”**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 50 mm f/1.4 USM

Settings:

50 mm | F/3.2 | ISO 320 | 1/1000 s

**Image No. 13 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Editing exposure, shadow, contrast and saturation
- Framing
- Convert the image to black and white

Light scheme

Light source: daylight.

Photo No. 14

**"In Order Not to Cry,
I Laughed..."**
from the Master's
photo art project
"Never Again?!"

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark IV /
Canon EF 50 mm f/1.4 USM

Settings:

50 mm | F 1.8 | ISO 320 | 1/1000 s

**Image No. 14 editing with
Adobe Photoshop 2022:**

- Editing exposure, shadow, contrast and saturation
- Framing

Light scheme
Light source: daylight.

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